

THE CHEMOTHERAPY OF BACTERIAL INFECTIONS. PART I. SYNTHESIS OF SOME DERIVATIVES OF SULPHANILAMIDE.

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In view of the recent discovery of the curative effects of sulphanilamide and many of its derivatives in the infections due to the *cocci* and other bacteria, it was thought worth while to prepare the gold salts of the allylthiourea derivatives of the above mentioned compounds for testing also in the case of tuberculosis. The syntheses of compounds of the general formula $p\text{-CH}_3\text{:CH}\cdot\text{CH}_2\text{NH}\cdot\text{CS}\cdot\text{NH}\cdot\text{C}_6\text{H}_4\cdot\text{R}$ are described.

The striking discovery by Domagk (*Z. angew. Chem.*, 1935, **48**, 480 ; *Deuts. Med. Wochs*, 1935, **61**, 250) of the specific action of the red dye, 'Prontosil' (hydrochloride of 4'-sulphamide-2:4-diaminoazobenzene) against the β -hemolytic streptococci, and the subsequent observation that the simple sulphanilamide as also many related sulphur derivatives of the general formula, $p\text{-R}\cdot\text{NH}\cdot\text{C}_6\text{H}_4\cdot\text{SO}_2\cdot\text{R}'$, possess a similar chemotherapeutic effect not only against the streptococci but also many other bacteria (Buttle, *Proc. Roy. Soc. Med.*, 1937, **31**, 154 ; *Annales Medicochirurgicales*, 1938, **3**, No. 3 ; Horlein, *Rep. Brit. Assoc. Adv. Sci. Nottingham*, 1937, p. 347), have opened up a new chapter in the chemotherapy of the bacterial diseases. It was, hence, thought worth while to prepare the gold salts of some of their derivatives with a view to study their suitability for treatment of tuberculosis.

One of the requisite properties of the gold salts suitable for the treatment of tuberculosis is that they should be stable to such an extent that after injection they may not easily decompose in the lymph with the rapid liberation of the metal. Though the researches of Kharash (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1931, **53**, 3053) have made available many gold compounds wherein the gold atom is directly attached to the benzene ring (just as in the case of arsenic or antimony), yet they are not entirely satisfactory for the present purpose. The aurothio (-SAu) combination which can be derived from a thiophenol or thiourea derivative is a stable union. In view of the fact that the thiophenols in general are more toxic than thioureas and that 'thiosinamine' (ω -allylthiourea) is well known for its bactericidal properties, attempts have now been made to prepare allylthiourea derivatives of the general formula (I) so that their gold salts can be tried in tuberculosis. It will be noticed that such gold salts possess a close relationship with the drug 'lopion' (gold salt of II).

In this paper some compounds of the general formula (I), synthesised according to the following general scheme, are described :

In some compounds, the radical R carries an acid grouping so that the final compounds may be used as salts soluble in water. The intermediate compounds of the type (III) are also being pharmacologically investigated. Recently Kolloff (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1938, 60, 950) has also synthesised compounds of this type, a note on the synthesis of some of which has already been published by the author (*Current Science*, 1938, 6, 608). Such compounds as have been described by Kolloff are, therefore, omitted. All the allylthiourea derivatives so far obtained yield with potassium chloroaurate under the usual conditions the corresponding gold salts.

The synthesis of similar allylthiourea derivatives of diphenyl sulphides, sulphones and sulphoxides will be described in the succeeding communication.

Incidentally, some compounds have been synthesised wherein the carboxyl group (Formula II) is replaced by other acid groupings which are well known for their bactericidal properties.

The compounds are being pharmacologically tested and the results will be described elsewhere.

E X P E R I M E N T A L.

The yields in all the following experiments are always very good unless otherwise stated.

Attempts to Prepare m-Aminophenyl- α -allylthiourea, NH₂·C₆H₄·NH·CS·NH·CH₂:CH:CH₂.—On boiling one molecule of *m*-phenylenediamine with exactly one molecule of allylthiocyanate, shining plates, m.p. 95-102°, were obtained, identified as *m*-phenylene-bis-(α -allylthiourea). (Found : N, 18.1. C₁₄H₁₈N₄S₂ : N, 18.3 per cent). (*cf.* Lellmann, *Annalen*, 1883, 221, 26). No monoallylthiourea derivative could be isolated.

m-Nitroacetanilide (6 g.) was reduced with iron dust (3 g.) according to the method of Mills (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1895, 67, 927) and the ammoniacal solution concentrated on the water-bath. When free from ammonia, to the solution (after filtration) allylthiocyanate (3 g.) and sufficient alcohol for solution were added and the whole refluxed for 1 hour on the steam-bath. On allowing to cool, *m*-acetaminophenyl- ω -allylthiourea separated in a crystalline form. Crystallised from dilute alcohol in shining leaflets it had m.p. 182°. (Found: N, 16.6; S, 12.6. $C_{12}H_{14}ON_2S$ requires N, 16.9; S, 12.9 per cent).

The above acetyl compound could be hydrolysed to the corresponding amine by boiling with (1:1) hydrochloric acid for a few minutes; it is fairly difficult to get the hydrochloride quite pure and the free amine is too unstable for purification and analysis.

p-Acetaminophenyl- ω -allylthiourea, $CH_3 \cdot CONH \cdot C_6H_4 \cdot NH \cdot CS \cdot NH \cdot CH_2 \cdot CH : CH_2$.—As in the case of *m*-phenylenediamine, *p*-phenylenediamine (1 mol) gave on boiling for one hour in alcoholic solution with one molecule of allylthiocyanate di- ω -allylthiourea derivative which crystallised from alcohol in prismatic needles, m.p. 200°. (Found: N, 18.4. $C_{14}H_{18}N_2S_2$ requires N, 18.3 per cent).

p-Acetphenylenediamine (5 g.), allylthiocyanate (2.6 g.) and ethyl alcohol (40 c.c.) were refluxed on the steam-bath for 1 hour, the solution diluted with water till a turbidity appeared, and allowed to cool when the condensation product separated in chains of rectangular plates. Recrystallised from dilute alcohol it had m.p. 175°. (Found: N, 17.0; S, 12.8. $C_{12}H_{15}ON_2S$ requires N, 16.9; S, 12.9 per cent).

p-Aminophenyl- ω -allylthiourea, $NH_2 \cdot C_6H_4 \cdot NH \cdot CS \cdot NH \cdot CH_2 \cdot CH : CH_2$.—The foregoing acetyl compound (2 g.) was boiled for 15 minutes with hydrochloric acid (1:1; 10 c.c.). The solution was allowed to evaporate at room temperature when the aminohydrochloride separated. It crystallised from ethyl alcohol in nodules, m.p. 230°. [Found: N, 14.6; Cl, 25.3; Equiv., 142. $C_{10}H_{13}N_2S_2 \cdot 2HCl$ requires N, 15.0; Cl, 25.3 per cent. Eqiv. (diacidic base), 140].

The hydrochloride on decomposition yielded the base which slowly crystallised from dilute alcohol in beautiful rhombic plates, m.p. 118-20°, but on exposure to air it rapidly turns brown and dark. It did not couple with diazotised *p*-sulphanilamide.

p-(ω -Allylthiourea)-cinnamic Acid, $\text{CH}_2\text{:CH}\cdot\text{CH}_2\cdot\text{NH}\cdot\text{CS}\cdot\text{NH}\cdot\text{C}_6\text{H}_4\cdot\text{CH}\cdot\text{CH}\cdot\text{CO}_2\text{H}$.—A mixture of *p*-aminocinnamic acid (4 g.) and allylisothiocyanate (2.5 g.) in dilute alcohol (50% ; 100 c.c.) was refluxed on the steam-bath for 1½ hours, cooled, diluted and left overnight. The product which separated crystallised from boiling water in light yellow prisms or plates, m.p. 171°. (Found: N, 10.5 ; S, 12.0 ; Equiv., 264.7. $\text{C}_{13}\text{H}_{14}\text{O}_2\text{N}_2\text{S}$ requires N, 10.7 ; S, 12.2 per cent. Equiv., 262).

m-(ω -Allylthiourea)-cinnamic Acid.—*m*-Aminocinnamic acid (2 g.), allylisothiocyanate (1.5 g.), sodium hydroxide (2*N*, 7 c.c.) and alcohol (30 c.c.) was refluxed for 1½ hours, the solution was cooled, diluted and acidified when the condensation product separated. It was crystallised from dilute alcohol in fine clusters of colourless needles, m.p. 177° (decomp.). (Found: N, 10.8. $\text{C}_{13}\text{H}_{14}\text{O}_2\text{N}_2\text{S}$ requires N, 10.7 per cent).

p-(ω -Allylthiourea) - phenylsulphamide, $\text{CH}_2\text{:CH}\cdot\text{CH}_2\cdot\text{NH}\cdot\text{CS}\cdot\text{NH}\cdot\text{C}_6\text{H}_4\cdot\text{SO}_2\text{NH}_2$.—Sulphanilic acid or its sodium salt failed to condense with allylisothiocyanate under the usual conditions. But *p*-sulphanilamide (4 g.), allylisothiocyanate (2 g.) and alcohol (50 c.c.), refluxed for one hour, yielded the crystalline allylthiourea derivative which was recrystallised from alcohol in shining colourless needles, m.p. 182°. (Found: N, 15.6 ; S, 23.5. $\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_{13}\text{O}_2\text{N}_3\text{S}$ requires N, 15.5 ; S, 23.6 per cent).

p-(ω -Allylthiourea)-phenylsulphonyl-*p*'-sulphonamidoanilide.— $\text{CH}_2\text{:CH}\cdot\text{CH}_2\cdot\text{NH}\cdot\text{CS}\cdot\text{NH}\cdot\text{C}_6\text{H}_4\cdot\text{SO}_2\text{NH}\cdot\text{C}_6\text{H}_4\cdot\text{SO}_2\text{NH}_2$.—This was prepared as above by boiling equimolecular quantities of 'disulphonamide or desepthal C' (prepared by the method of Gray, Buttle and Stephenson, *Biochem. J.*, 1937, 81, 727) and allylthioisocyanate in ethyl alcohol. The product crystallised from dilute alcohol, m.p. 180-81° (decomp.). (Found: N, 12.8. $\text{C}_{16}\text{H}_{19}\text{O}_4\text{N}_4\text{S}_2$ requires N, 13.2 per cent).

p-Acetaminophenyldimethylsulphonamide. $\text{Ac}\cdot\text{NH}\cdot\text{C}_6\text{H}_4\cdot\text{SO}_2\text{NMe}_2$.—A mixture of *p*-acetaminobenzene sulphochloride (5 g.) in benzene and a benzene solution (33%) of diethylamine (5 c.c.) were allowed to stand with good shaking for several hours, then filtered and the product, washed well with water, and crystallised from water in beautiful square plates, m.p. 143°. (Found: N, 11.4. $\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_{14}\text{O}_2\text{N}_2\text{S}$ requires N, 11.6 per cent).

p-Aminophenyldimethylsulphonamide, $\text{NH}_2\cdot\text{C}_6\text{H}_4\cdot\text{SO}_2\cdot\text{NMe}_2$.—This compound is mentioned in patent D.R.P. 607,537 (*Friedlan.* 1937, 21, 557) and also by Trefouel, Nitti and Bovet (*Annales de l' Inst. Pasteur*, 1937, 88, 33), but does not appear to have been described anywhere. The foregoing acetyl compound (3.6 g.) was refluxed with hydrochloric acid (5*N*, 12 c.c.) for ½ hour, the clear solution basified with ammonia after cooling and the product which separated was filtered, washed and crystallised

from alcohol in rhombic plates, m.p. 172°. (Found : N, 14'0 ; S, 15'7. $C_8H_{12}O_2N_2S$ requires N, 14'0 ; S, 16'0 per cent).

p-(*ω*-Allylthiourea)-phenyldimethylsulphonamide, $CH_2 \cdot CH \cdot CH_2 \cdot NH \cdot CS \cdot NH \cdot C_6H_4 \cdot SO_2 \cdot NMe_2$.—Equimolecular quantities of *p*-aminophenyldimethylsulphonamide and allylthiocyanate were boiled for 1 hour in alcohol and the resulting product crystallised from dilute alcohol, m.p. 181°. (Found : N, 13'9 ; S, 21'1. $C_{12}H_{17}O_2N_2S_2$ requires N, 14'0 ; S, 21'4 per cent).

p-Acetaminophenylsulphonyl-*p*'-dimethylamidoanilide, $CH_3 \cdot CONH \cdot C_6H_4 \cdot SO_2 \cdot NH \cdot C_6H_4 \cdot NMe_2$.—*p*-Acetaminobenzene sulphochloride (1 mol.) and *p*-aminodimethylaniline (little over 2 mols., freshly prepared) were mixed together in ether solution with frequent shaking and allowed to stand overnight. The crystalline product which separated was washed with water and recrystallised from alcohol (charcoal) in beautiful plates, m.p. 196°. (Found : N, 12'5. $C_{16}H_{19}O_2N_2S$ requires N, 12'6 per cent).

p-Aminophenylsulphonyl-*p*'-dimethylaminoanilide, $NH_2 \cdot C_6H_4 \cdot SO_2 \cdot NH \cdot C_6H_4 \cdot NMe_2$.—This compound has been referred to as 'Uliron' by Domagk (*Klin. Wochschr.*, 1937, 16, 1412 ; cf. Buttle, *Proc. Roy. Soc. Med.*, 1937, 51, 156). It is to be noted that Fourneau, Trefonel, Nitti and Bovet (*Compt. rend. Soc. Biol.*, 1938, 127, 393) assign the constitution *p*-aminophenylsulphonyl-*p*'-amidophenyldimethylsulphonamide to 'Uliron' (cf. Palazzoli and Bovet, *Annales Médico-Chirurgicales*, 1938, 3, No. 3, p. 93). No description of this compound, however, is available. This was prepared by the hydrolysis (5*N*-HCl) of the above acetyl derivative. It crystallised from alcohol in shining prismatic needles, m.p. 231°. (Found : N, 14'4. $C_{16}H_{17}O_2N_2S$ requires N, 14'4 per cent).

This compound does not condense with allylthiocyanate under usual conditions. But on boiling for 5 hours with allylthiocyanate it gives the corresponding allylthiourea derivative which crystallised from dilute alcohol in shining rhombic plates, m.p. 161°. (Found : N, 14'1. $C_{18}H_{22}O_2N_4S_2$ requires N, 14'4 per cent).

p-Aminophenylsulphonyl-*p*'-amidoanilide, $NH_2 \cdot C_6H_4 \cdot SO_2 \cdot NH \cdot C_6H_4 \cdot NH_2$.—A mixture of *p*-acetaminophenyl sulphochloride (4 g.), *p*-acetphenylenediamine (5'5 g.) and water (100 c.c.) was well ground in a mortar for 3 hours, filtered and the product washed. *p*-Acetaminophenylsulphonyl-*p*'-amidoanilide thus obtained, is very sparingly soluble in all solvents and was purified by dissolving in dilute sodium hydroxide and precipitating with acetic acid (m.p. about 320°). This product (2'5 g.) was boiled with hydrochloric acid (6*N*, 25 c.c.) for 1 hour, and the clear solution made just alkaline with ammonia when on cooling the amine separated in fine

needles or nodules. Crystallised from dilute alcohol in clusters of woolly needles it had m.p. 155°. (Found: N, 16.1. $C_{12}H_{13}O_2N_2S$ requires N, 16.0 per cent).

On boiling the above amino compound with 2 molecules of allylthiocyanate a product, which separated as oil and solidified on standing and scratching, crystallised from dilute alcohol, m.p. 175°. [Found: N, 15.21; S, 18.1. $C_{14}H_{16}O_2N_2S$ (monothiourea derivative) requires N, 15.5; S, 17.7 per cent. $C_{20}H_{22}O_2N_2S_2$ (dithiourea derivative) requires N, 15.2; S, 20.8 per cent].

p-Acetaminobenzenesulphonyl-*m*'-amidocinnamic Acid, $Ac \cdot NH \cdot C_6H_4 \cdot SO_2NH \cdot C_6H_4 \cdot CH : CH \cdot CO_2H$.—*m*-Aminocinnamic acid (3.2 g.), *p*-acetaminobenzene sulphochloride (2.3 g.) and water (100 c. c.) were ground together and allowed to stand for 4 hours with frequent shaking. The insoluble residue was filtered and crystallised from dilute alcohol in fine shining needles, m.p. 231° (decomp.). (Found: N, 7.7. $C_{17}H_{16}O_4N_2S$ requires N, 7.8 per cent). The condensation can also be effected in presence of alkali by using molecular proportions of the reactants.

p-Aminobenzenesulphonyl-*m*'-amidocinnamic Acid.—The hydrolysis of the above acetyl compound with hydrochloric acid was not satisfactory. The alkaline hydrolysis by the following method gave far better results. The acetyl compound was dissolved in about 40% sodium hydroxide and warmed on the water-bath for 10 minutes. It was then diluted with a little water and warmed further for about 20 minutes. On cooling and carefully acidifying the alkaline solution, the amino acid was precipitated. It crystallised from water in needles or from dilute alcohol in silky needles or rhombic plates, m.p. 213°. (Found: N, 8.4, 8.7; S, 9.8. $C_{15}H_{14}O_4N_2S$ requires N, 8.8; S, 10.1 per cent).

p-Acetaminobenzenesulphonyl-*p*'-amidocinnamic Acid.—This was prepared exactly as the above described *m*-isomer. It crystallised from dilute alcohol in light yellow nodules, m.p. 252° (decomp.). (Found: N, 7.4. $C_{17}H_{16}O_5N_2S$ requires N, 7.8 per cent).

p-Aminobenzenesulphonyl-*p*'-amidocinnamic acid was prepared as the *meta* isomer by the alkaline hydrolysis of the corresponding acetyl compound. Crystallised from dilute alcohol in prismatic needles it had m.p. 239° (decomp.). (Found: S, 9.9. $C_{15}H_{14}O_4N_2S$ requires S, 10.1 per cent).

m-Aminomandelic acid undergoes a similar condensation and the product will be described in the succeeding communication.

p-Acetaminobenzenesulphonamidoethyl Acetate, $Ac \cdot NH \cdot C_6H_4 \cdot SO_2NH \cdot CH_2 \cdot CO_2C_2H_5$.—To a solution of glycine ester hydrochloride (5.5 g.) and

sodium hydroxide (2*N*, 25 c.c.) was added *p*-acetamidobenzene sulphochloride (5 g.) dissolved in alcohol (50 c. c.). After allowing to stand overnight, the solution was concentrated and the condensation product isolated by cooling. It crystallised from dilute alcohol in fine needles, m. p. 129°. (Found: N, 9.3; S, 10.3. $C_{12}H_{10}O_2N_2S$ requires N, 9.3; S, 10.7 per cent).

p-Aminobenzenesulphonamidoacetic Acid Hydrochloride, $NH_2 \cdot C_6H_4 \cdot SO_2NH \cdot CH_2 \cdot CO_2H$, HCl.—The above ester (3.5 g.) was refluxed for 1 hour with hydrochloric acid (5 *N*, 12 c. c.). The solution was concentrated when the crystalline hydrochloride separated. It was crystallised from alcohol in nodules of fine needles, m. p. 172° (decomp.). (Found: N, 9.9; Cl, 12.8. $C_8H_{11}O_4N_2ClS$ requires N, 10.5; Cl, 13.3 per cent). The free base, m. p. 151°, has been described by Kolloff (*loc. cit.*).

Condensations with other amino-acids such as glutamic acid, leucine, aspartic acid, etc., will be published later on.

p-Aminobenzenesulphonamidobenzene-*p*'-sulphonic Acid, $NH_2 \cdot C_6H_4 \cdot SO_2NH \cdot C_6H_4 \cdot SO_3H$.—The preparation of this compound was described by the author (*loc. cit.*) in a note and recently Kolloff (*loc. cit.*) has described its synthesis; the details are omitted here.

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